

Skillful heat-related mortality forecasting during recent deadly European summers

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Europe is a heatwave hotspot: numerous temperature records have been broken in recent summers, and roughly 60,000 and 50,000 heat-related deaths occurred in the summers of 2022 and 2023, respectively. With recent summers, like that of 2022, projected to become the new norm, there is a pressing need to further develop heat-health warning systems to help society adapt to a warming climate. Here, we forecast heat-related mortality by applying a statistical epidemiological framework to temperature forecasts extending up to two weeks in advance. Focusing on two recent and exceptional summers in Europe, namely 2022 and 2023, we evaluate the skill of the daily heat-related mortality forecasts, and assess its association with temperature. For most of Europe, milder temperatures, close to the minimum mortality temperature, are associated with more skillful heat-related mortality forecasts. However, some of the hottest regions in Europe instead showed enhanced forecast skill associated with higher temperatures. This suggests that heat-related mortality forecasts can provide valuable information in European regions associated with high levels of heat-related mortality. Consequently, we advocate for local health authorities to include information from forecasts of heat-related mortality in their heat warning systems.

Heat-related mortality | early-warning systems | impact forecasting | temperature extremes | Europe

Recent years have repeatedly witnessed unprecedented temperatures, with the summers of 2022 and 2023 being the warmest on record for Europe and globally, respectively (1, 2), at the time of occurrence. Europe in particular is emerging as a heatwave hotspot (3), against the background of a global increase in heatwave frequency, duration and intensity under climate change (4). Extreme temperatures are linked to multifarious detrimental human health impacts, notably excess mortality (5–7), and increased extreme heat in Europe imposes a heavy burden on society. The European summer of 2022 was associated with over 60,000 heat-related deaths (8), followed by over 47,000 heat-related deaths in 2023 (9).

(9) showed that the 2023 heat-related mortality (HRM) burden would have been 80% higher without adaptation processes that occurred in Europe this century. The importance of adaptation is evidenced by the case-in-point of the summers of 2003 and 2006. The summer of 2003 witnessed over 70,000 excess deaths in Europe (10), and resulted in the implementation of heat early-warning systems in several European countries (11). The summer of 2006 again saw parts of Europe experience a severe heatwave. However, in France the observed mortality was markedly less than expected (12), which was partially attributed to the implementation of early-warning systems after the 2003 heatwave (12). With summers like the aforementioned projected to become the new norm in the coming decades, the seasonal distribution of deaths will rapidly change. The increase in HRM will outstrip the decrease in cold-related mortality by the second half of the century for most future climate scenarios (13) unless further adaptations to rising temperatures occur. Heat-health early-warning systems (e.g. 14) are one such key adaptation, supporting the broader effort to adapt society to a changing climate.

Here, we analyse whether numerical forecasts of temperature enable skillful forecasts of HRM on time scales of several days to two weeks, which forms the core of effective heat-health early-warning systems. We consider the European summers of 2022 and 2023, which are of particular interest for the study of the practical predictability of HRM. Firstly, they exemplify the occurrence of deadly heat in Europe. Secondly, unprecedented temperatures such as those during those two summers are projected to become increasingly common, and are thereby representative of summers to come. Finally, numerical weather prediction (NWP) models are regularly updated to improve model performance, and, on average, forecast capabilities have improved by about 1 day every 10 years (15). Selecting

Significance Statement

Heat-related mortality is a growing issue in Europe, and the continued development of heat warning systems is a key aspect of society's adaptation to a changing climate. To date, many heat warning systems across Europe consider human-health impacts only implicitly. Here, we place the explicit focus on human-health impacts. Specifically, we assess the pan-European skill of heat-related mortality forecasts for 2022 and 2023; two exceptionally hot summers. Our findings demonstrate regionally and temperature dependent skill for heat-related mortality forecasts. We further note enhanced skill during particularly hot conditions, and thus advocate for the adoption of information from impact-based forecasts in heat warning systems. This information has the potential to be particularly beneficial in helping protect vulnerable members of society.

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249 recent summers thus ensures that the analysis is conducted
250 on forecasts which are close to current NWP capabilities.

251 (16) show that the intensity of temperature extremes can
252 in general be forecasted 1–3 weeks in advance, whilst (17)
253 showed that temperature-related mortality could in general
254 be forecast more than 8 days in advance based on forecast
255 capabilities prior to 2020. To assess the practical predictability
256 of HRM during recent record-breaking summers we compute
257 HRM forecasts based on temperature forecasts, leveraging the
258 epidemiological association between temperature and HRM.
259 This association is estimated using a non-linear statistical
260 model, meaning that the errors of the HRM forecast may
261 differ to those of the original temperature forecasts. It
262 is thus crucial to investigate the predictability properties
263 of HRM forecasts. To achieve this we first analyse the
264 relationship between temperature and mortality, and the
265 spatial distribution of HRM. We then assess the temporal
266 evolution of temperature and HRM. Finally, we investigate
267 the temporal and spatial distribution of HRM forecast skill
268 for several European regions, ultimately offering a spatially-
269 and temporally-resolved quantification of the relationship
270 between temperature and HRM forecast skill in Europe. Fig.
271 1a provides a graphical summary of the connection between
272 the sets of analysis in this study.

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275 1. Results

276 First, we show a visual summary of the analysis conducted in
277 this study (Fig. 1a). We begin the analysis by examining the
278 relationship between temperature and mortality from both
279 continental-average and regional perspectives. The pooled
280 exposure-response association (Fig. 1b) shows a clear non-
281 linear relationship between temperature and RR, which is
282 especially prominent for heat (temperatures to the right of
283 the curve’s minimum). This minimum point, namely the
284 MMT, shows a marked north-south gradient, with countries
285 bordering the Mediterranean showing the highest values,
286 and more northerly or elevated regions showing lower values
287 (Fig. 1d). The pooled lag-response association at the 99th
288 percentile shows a rapid decay in RR with time after exposure
289 (Fig. 1c). The cumulative RR at the 99th percentile of
290 temperatures (Fig. 1e) again shows a north-south gradient.

291 We now extend our analysis by considering this
292 temperature–mortality relationship from a forecasting per-
293 spective. Specifically, we investigate the time series of
294 daily temperature and AF averaged over almost all regions
295 in Europe for the summers of 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 2).
296 These two summers were characterised by consistently above-
297 climatology temperatures, with several heatwave periods
298 when temperatures exceeded climatology by 4°C or more (Fig.
299 2a,b). As expected, the seven-day lead-time forecasts more
300 closely resembled the observations than forecasts with lead-
301 time 14 days. The continental-mean AF (Fig. 2c–f) broadly
302 follows the peaks of the temperature time series, although the
303 non-linear epidemiological relationship amplifies AF during
304 periods of elevated temperatures. Thus, even a moderate
305 temperature forecast spread at elevated temperatures leads
306 to a large AF forecast spread (Fig. 2c,d). Furthermore,
307 the uncertainty due to the epidemiological fit is also largest
308 for the most elevated temperatures (Fig. 2e,f). We show
309 the spatial distributions of seasonal-average temperature and
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311 AF for the summers of 2022 and 2023 in Figs. 1,2,3 of the
312 appendix.

313 Next we evaluate the forecasts to assess how many days in
314 advance the forecasts typically provide ‘useful’ information.
315 For both temperature and AF, the predictability horizon
316 varies between several days and almost two weeks, with
317 variations in the AF horizon often but not always matching
318 those in the temperature horizon (Fig. 3a–d, appendix:
319 Fig. 4). During summer 2022, south-western Europe shows
320 mostly enhanced temperature predictability relative to
321 the other regions (Fig. 3a). AF shows a predictability
322 peak for south-western Europe during July 2022 (Fig.
323 3c), which matches the temperature predictability peak.
324 This corresponds to record-breaking temperatures across
325 south-western Europe at that time. However, AF also
326 displays a prolonged period of heightened predictability in
327 south-eastern Europe starting at roughly the same time,
328 which is not clearly visible in temperature. In 2023, western
329 Europe shows a predictability peak in June, while south-
330 western and south-eastern Europe show prominent peaks
331 in July (Fig. 3b). During summer 2023, all macro-regions
332 display a peak in AF predictability horizon between early
333 and late July (Fig. 3d), even though western Europe and
334 Europe as a whole do not show particularly prominent
335 peaks in temperature predictability during the same time.
336 As evidenced by the differences between the four analysed
337 macro-regions, the predictability horizons also display a
338 marked spatial variability. In 2022, the predictability horizon
339 for temperature varies between approximately 4–8 days in
340 northern and north-western Europe, whilst reaching up to
341 12 days in parts of southern Europe (Fig. 3e). 2023 shows
342 a similar north-south gradient, albeit less pronounced than
343 for 2022 (Fig. 3f). During 2022, southern Europe showed a
344 reduced predictability horizon for AF relative to temperature,
345 with differences often in the range of 1–4 days (Fig. 3g,
346 appendix: Fig 5a). Northern Europe, including the British
347 Isles, instead showed an increased predictability horizon.
348 In 2023 the AF predictability horizon is generally higher
349 than for 2022 (Fig. 3h), and is longer than the temperature
350 horizon in many regions, notably in eastern and northern
351 Europe, and Portugal (appendix: Fig 5b).

352 To better understand the varying relationship between the
353 predictability of temperature and AF, we perform regressions
354 between several combinations of temperature, temperature
355 predictability horizon and AF predictability horizon. Sum-
356 mer 2022 displays significant positive regression-coefficients
357 between temperature and temperature predictability, and
358 positive coefficients for temperature predictability versus
359 AF predictability in some parts of France, Spain and Italy
360 bordering the Mediterranean (Fig. 4a,c). Thus, higher
361 temperatures generally benefit temperature predictability,
362 which in turn benefits AF predictability for some parts of the
363 Mediterranean coastline. Positive coefficients for temperature
364 versus temperature predictability are also visible for summer
365 2023, with southern and south-eastern Europe showing a more
366 pronounced signal than in 2022 (Fig. 4b). However, the signal
367 is weakened when considering temperature predictability ver-
368 sus AF predictability (Fig. 4d). The differences between the
369 two summers become evident when regressing temperature
370 against AF predictability (Figs. 4e,f). In summer 2022 there
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Fig. 1. Summary graphic of the analysis in this study (a), curves showing the pooled, population-weighted European average of both the association between temperature and the relative risk of mortality (RR) (b) and the lag response at the 99th percentile of temperature (c) where the 95% confidence interval is shaded. The dashed horizontal lines in (b, c) denote RR = 1. Maps of the minimum mortality temperature (MMT) for each region (d) and the RR at the 99th percentile for each region (e). Missing data is in white (d,e).

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Fig. 2. Time series of 2m temperature (temperature, K) (a,b), and Attributable Fraction (AF,%) (c-f) for the summers (June-August) of 2022 (a,c,e) and 2023 (b,d,f). Dashed black denotes climatology, solid black denotes observations, red denotes forecast values (median) at lead time 7 days and blue denotes forecast values (median) at lead time 14 days. For panels a-d we show the median of the forecast ensemble, whilst in panels e,f we show the median from the Monte-Carlo simulations. The shading shows the forecast ensemble spread for temperature (a,b), and AF (c,d) and the 95% confidence interval from the epidemiological fit (e,f). Values are population-weighted averages of all analysed European regions.

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Fig. 3. Time series' of 2m temperature (temperature; a,b) and Attributable Fraction (AF; c,d) predictability horizons, for Europe (black), south-western Europe (orange), western Europe (blue) and south-eastern Europe (red) for 2022 (a,c) and 2023 (b,d). Shading denotes the 95% confidence interval determined by bootstrapping the regions of the dataset. Values have been population-weighted prior to averaging. Composites of the predictability horizon of temperature (e,f) and AF (g,h) for 2022 (e,g) and 2023 (f,h). Missing data is shown in white.

Fig. 4. Coefficients estimated from negative binomial regression fits for 2m temperature (temperature) vs the predictability horizon of temperature (a,b), the predictability horizon of temperature vs the predictability horizon of Attributable Fraction (AF) (c,d) and temperature vs the predictability horizon of AF (e,f) in 2022 (a,c,e) and 2023 (b,d,f). The significance of the regression coefficients was corrected for multiple tests following (18). Non-significant values are shaded light grey; missing data is in white.

Summary of predictability for temperature and AF

	Temperature	AF
Region	north-south gradient; higher predictability in southern regions	north-south gradient; higher predictability in northern regions
Year	Higher predictability for 2022 than 2023	Higher predictability on average for 2023 than 2022 (climatologically cooler places)
Region and year	High predictability during the hottest part of 2022 for southern Europe	High predictability during the hottest part of 2022 for southern Europe

Table 1. Summary of the results varying by region, year, and the combination of region and year.

is a significant positive relationship in some regions bordering Mediterranean, and either no significant relationship or a negative relationship elsewhere in the rest of Europe. Summer 2023 displays a widespread significant negative relationship, which is particularly pronounced along the Atlantic coast but also present along the Mediterranean coastline. This indicates that milder temperatures lead to an increased AF predictability horizon. We summarise these results in Table 1, which provides an overview of the predictability of temperature and AF by year and region.

2. Discussion

Our analysis highlights the non-linear, and spatio-temporally varying relationship between temperature and AF in a predictability context. For most of Europe, AF forecasts show reduced skill during the hottest days of summer due to the epidemiological transformation. This means that results from the literature on the evaluation of temperature forecasts cannot be easily translated to AF forecasts. Nonetheless, the two are not entirely decoupled, and particularly large forecast errors for temperature (so-called "forecast busts" (19, 20)) may also detract from AF predictability, especially if such busts occur during a heatwave.

Summertime temperature extremes in Europe result from multiple processes occurring across different spatial scales (21). There are nonetheless specific large-scale circulation patterns associated with elevated temperatures across the continent, notably persistent high-pressure features termed atmospheric blocking (e.g. 22). The mature phase of blocking has been associated with enhanced operational predictability, whilst blocking onset and decay remain challenging to forecast (23, 24), potentially leading to large errors in temperature forecasts. This may in turn have direct consequences for AF forecasts. Summer 2022 was characterised by a blocked flow pattern over western and north-western Europe during June and July (25), which then decayed in late July. The imperfect representation of such flow patterns could explain the comparatively poor 14-day temperature forecast for late July 2022 (Fig. 2a), which did not capture the temporary decrease in temperatures seen in observations. We posit that improvements in NWP models' capabilities of capturing the onset and decay of blocking events would be of direct relevance to AF forecasting.

Indeed, forecast errors at high temperatures are amplified during the transformation to AF, due to the non-linear relationship between the two (Fig. 1b). This non-linear relationship between temperature and AF is also reflected

in the transformation of temperature forecast spread to its AF counterpart. Unlike temperature, AF is bounded from below at 0, naturally giving an asymmetry in forecast spread. This asymmetry is also evident for forecasts of larger AF, where ensemble members with higher values for temperature correspond to amplified AF values, whilst temperature values closer to the minimum mortality temperature show a compressed spread in the AF forecast (Fig. 2c,d). We argue that improvements in NWP model performance associated specifically with hot temperatures would be particularly valuable for improving the accuracy of HRM forecasts. Furthermore, the use of data-driven forecast models could represent a fruitful line of inquiry if such models could be specifically tailored either to perform well for hot temperatures when health impacts are greatest, or to directly forecast heat-health impacts (26).

Assuming that each ensemble member of any given temperature forecast represents a physically plausible evolution of temperature over Europe, it is possible to attain temperatures corresponding to AF values which are much larger than those we estimated here for the summers of 2022 and 2023. Furthermore, we suggest that recent studies considering worst-case heatwave scenarios (e.g. 27, 28) could be examined using the methodology employed here to help guide preparedness plans. However, we acknowledge the caveat that the epidemiological model employed here is only trained on temperatures that have been observed, meaning that estimations of AF associated with record-breaking temperatures should be considered cautiously.

(29) find that heat warnings based on fixed-temperature thresholds underestimate the number of days when heat affects the population, and call for better alignment between the issuing of heat warnings and societal responses to heat. Impact-based forecasts have the advantage of providing relevant information specifically tailored to the societal response. In order to inform the issuing of vulnerability-specific warnings by heat-health warning systems, epidemiological models could be extended to consider physiological factors (e.g. sex, age, comorbidities), or even socio-economic vulnerabilities.

Our results evidence a regionally-varying temperature-dependent skill of AF forecasts, and we highlight the parts of France, Spain and Italy bordering Mediterranean as a particularly interesting case. In 2022, a coherent, statistically significant relationship between temperature and the predictability horizon of AF is visible there (Fig. 4e), which also broadly corresponds to the regions highlighted in

993 Fig. 1a of the appendix as having the largest AF values, and 1055
994 where the seasonal-mean temperature is well above the MMT 1056
995 (appendix: Fig. 6a). We conjecture that these extreme 1057
996 temperatures seen along parts of the Mediterranean coastline 1058
997 correspond to the far right end of the temperature-RR curve 1059
998 (Fig. 1b), where the relationship is strongly non-linear. 1060
999 Consequently, climatology – which we take as a baseline 1061
1000 against which we evaluate our forecasts– would provide 1062
1001 a poor estimate of AF. On the other hand, an inverse 1063
1002 association between temperature and the predictability 1064
1003 horizon of AF can be seen along Europe’s Atlantic coast 1065
1004 (Fig. 4e,f). This region is climatologically cooler than the 1066
1005 Mediterranean basin, with mean temperatures for the season 1067
1006 only slightly above the MMT (appendix: Fig. 6). We 1068
1007 thus conjecture that here the relationship is dominated by 1069
1008 comparatively good AF forecast performance corresponding 1070
1009 to cooler temperatures, close to the MMT. For temperatures 1071
1010 close to the MMT the RR curve is relatively flat, meaning 1072
1011 that temperature errors in this vicinity would be of little 1073
1012 importance to the AF, which would have a value close to 0. 1074

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1014 We acknowledge a number of limitations of this study. 1075
1015 First and foremost we consider only the summers of 2022 1076
1016 and 2023. These years were chosen so as to focus on recent 1077
1017 and particularly hot summers. Whilst we argue that they 1078
1018 exemplify projected future summers, the small sample 1079
1019 size curtails making reliable generalisations, and further 1080
1020 verification of the findings presented here is imperative. This 1081
1021 should include the use of observed mortality data, where 1082
1022 available. Indeed, the verification approach we adopted 1083
1023 here is akin to the perfect model approach (30), as AF 1084
1024 forecasts are verified against AF estimations from reanalysis 1085
1025 temperature data. A further limitation is the correction 1086
1026 of systematic errors in temperature forecasts. Here we 1087
1027 adopted a computationally advantageous method, which is 1088
1028 however not tailored to AF forecasts. In order to generate 1089
1029 optimal AF forecasts, we suggest that temperature forecasts 1090
1030 should undergo a tailored bias correction accounting for 1091
1031 the non-linear relationship between temperature and AF. 1092
1032 At the time of this study, data for some regions was not 1093
1033 accessible, particularly in north-eastern Europe. Continued 1094
1034 efforts to improve the accessibility of health data are vital 1095
1035 for the development of the heat-health field, and to address 1096
1036 biases in the focus regions of studies (31). In particular, the 1097
1037 methodology presented here could be expanded to different 1098
1038 geographical regions, and we highlight the need for further 1099
1039 studies targeting regions in the global south. Our results 1100
1040 suggest that such forecasts could be useful for summers 1101
1041 hotter than 2022 and 2023, although it is not possible to 1102
1042 verify this until such summers occur. The use of climate 1103
1043 models could provide a useful avenue of research to simulate 1104
1044 potential future record-breaking events, whilst the use of 1105
1045 reforecast data from weather models could prove informative 1106
1046 for a systematic verification of current forecast capabilities, 1107
1047 albeit for hypothetical scenarios. 1108

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1049 Finally, our findings have important implications in the 1109
1050 context of a warming climate. In the absence of meaningful 1110
1051 adaptation measures or major advances in NWP modelling, 1111
1052 AF forecasts in many European regions will be associated with 1112
1053 larger forecast spread and errors for future, unprecedentedly 1113
1054 1114

high temperatures. This is particularly pertinent for the 1055
Mediterranean basin, which is both climatologically warmer 1056
than the European average, and has been identified as a 1057
climate change hotspot (32). The study of future scenarios 1058
presents an important avenue for further research, and a key 1059
advantage of the methodology used here is that it could be gen- 1060
eralised to such set-ups. Furthermore, dynamical changes in 1061
the atmospheric circulation can reinforce the thermodynamic 1062
warming occurring at the surface (33). Different circulation 1063
patterns are associated with differing levels of predictability 1064
(23), and it is as yet uncertain how changes in their relative 1065
occurrence could influence the predictability of temperature 1066
and hence AF. Future studies could fruitfully investigate the 1067
link between flow patterns driving temperature extremes, 1068
the predictability of these flow patterns and how this could 1069
inform AF skill. 1070

3. Conclusions 1071

This study has considered the predictability of Europe-wide 1072
heat-related mortality in the context of numerical weather 1073
forecasts of temperature during the exceptionally warm 1074
summers of 2022 and 2023. The non-linear relationship 1075
between temperature and heat-related mortality has a marked 1076
effect on the propagation of forecast spread and error between 1077
the temperature and mortality forecasts, with the latter being 1078
particularly sensitive to errors in temperature forecasts at 1079
high temperatures. Nonetheless, in some of the hottest 1080
regions in Europe, mortality is more skillfully predicted 1081
for higher temperatures than low ones. This suggests that 1082
mortality forecasts can provide valuable information. How- 1083
ever, further interdisciplinary efforts are needed to overcome 1084
the challenges in forecasting mortality for the hottest and 1085
most deadly days. In the context of a warming climate, the 1086
continued development of heat-related mortality forecasts for 1087
early-warning systems is of the utmost importance in order to 1088
protect society from the increasing burden of extreme heat. 1089

Data Archival. The meteorological data used in this study 1090
can be downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Data 1091
Store <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>. The TIGGE fore- 1092
cast data is available at [https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/](https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/tigge/levtype=sfc/type=cf/) 1093
[tigge/levtype=sfc/type=cf/](https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/tigge/levtype=sfc/type=cf/) and the ERA5-Land reanalysis 1094
data is available at [https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/](https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=download) 1095
[reanalysis-era5-land?tab=download](https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=download). The health data used 1096
in this study cannot be made publicly available due to 1097
confidentiality agreements with data providers. 1098

Materials and Methods 1099

4. Data and Methods 1100

A. Mortality data. We used the spatio-temporally-homogeneous 1101
daily regional EARLY-ADAPT mortality database (34), which in 1102
the case of this study contains over 153 million death-counts for 31 1103
European countries. These represent the countries’ entire urban 1104
and rural population of over 504 million people. The data was 1105
reported for 580 contiguous regions as follows: Austria (35 regions), 1106
Belgium (40), Bosnia and Herzegovina (1), Bulgaria (6), Croatia 1107
(1), Cyprus (1), Czechia (14), Denmark (1), England (9), Estonia 1108
(1), France (96), Finland (4), Germany (16), Greece (46), Hungary 1109
(8), Ireland (1), Italy (99), Latvia (6), Lithuania (2), Luxembourg 1110
(1), Montenegro (1), the Netherlands (1), Norway (11), Portugal 1111
(7), Romania (42), Scotland (23), Serbia (24), Slovenia (12), 1112

1117 Slovakia (8), Spain (52), Sweden (3), Switzerland (7) and Wales (1).
 1118 When spatially aggregating data, we consider the following macro-
 1119 regions: south-western Europe (Spain and Portugal), south-eastern
 1120 Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Malta) and
 1121 western Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg and
 1122 the Netherlands). These groupings were chosen to approximately
 1123 correspond to the heatwave regions studied in (35).

1124 **B. Meteorological data.** We used daily averages of gridded 2m
 1125 temperature (temperature) from both the ERA5-land reanalysis
 1126 dataset (36) (temporal resolution: hourly; horizontal resolution:
 1127 0.1°), and a 51-member ensemble of archived operational fore-
 1128 casts from TIGGE (37) (temporal resolution: 6-hourly; spatial
 1129 resolution: 0.25°) with lead-times up to 14 days. We consider
 1130 forecasts from the summers of 2022 and 2023, which we verify
 1131 using ERA5-land from the same time period. The forecasts were
 1132 spatially aggregated to match the available regional mortality data.
 1133 Similarly, the ERA5-land data was weighted by population, then
 1134 spatially aggregated. The temperature climatology was calculated
 1135 by the day of year using ERA5-land data from 1991-2020, following
 1136 the WMO definition of climatological period, and smoothed with a
 1137 31-day running mean. Adopting the shorter period of 2010-2019 as
 1138 for the HRM results, on average, in a 0.28K warmer climatology.

1139 **C. Bias correction.** Forecasts are associated with systematic errors,
 1140 which typically increase with lead time. To account for these
 1141 systematic errors, we perform a bias correction. We use the BC-
 1142 30 method as in (17, 38, Section 3.2), for further details on the
 1143 computation see the Appendix. Given the high complexity of
 1144 epidemiological models transforming temperature forecasts into
 1145 health predictions, this method was chosen as a compromise
 1146 between complexity and accuracy due to its comparatively light
 1147 computational requirements. We acknowledge that alternative
 1148 methods may provide improved bias correction, albeit with
 1149 significantly increased computational expense. Further, we are not
 1150 aware of any systematic study analysing optimal bias correction
 1151 techniques for human-health impact studies.

1152 **D. Epidemiological model for temperature-related mortality.** The
 1153 temperature-related mortality was calculated with data repre-
 1154 senting the full year as in (39), which, along with numerous
 1155 other studies, builds on the work of (6). We have chosen this
 1156 setup so that this study may be extended, or operationalised,
 1157 for the full year using one continuous system for the consistent
 1158 forecasting of temperature-related mortality. The temperature-lag-
 1159 mortality relationship was estimated separately for each region
 1160 with temperature and mortality data from 2000-2019 using a quasi-
 1161 Poisson regression model:

$$1162 \log(E(M(t))) = I + DOW + S(t) + CB(t2m(t)), \quad [1]$$

1163 where $E(M(t))$ is the expected value of mortality for a given
 1164 day t , I is an intercept, DOW is the day of the week, $S(t)$
 1165 is a natural cubic spline with 8 degrees of freedom per year
 1166 accounting for seasonal and long-term trends, and $CB(t2m(t))$
 1167 is a cross-basis function used to estimate the exposure-lag-response
 1168 relation between daily temperature ($t2m$) and mortality (M)
 1169 values (40), with lags extending up to 21 days. The cross-basis
 1170 was modelled using natural cubic splines, with the exposure-
 1171 response function containing three internal knots at the 10th,
 1172 75th and 90th percentiles of the location-specific temperature
 1173 distribution, and the lag-response function was modelled with an
 1174 intercept and three internal knots equally spaced in the logarithmic
 1175 scale. The location-specific coefficients were then pooled using
 1176 a multivariate, multilevel meta-regression analysis. This meta-
 1177 regression comprised of two levels of random effects by regions
 1178 nested within countries, the location-specific temperature average
 1179 and the temperature inter-quartile range as meta-predictors. For
 1180 each region we calculated the best linear unbiased predictions of
 1181 the temperature-mortality relationship from the meta regression.
 1182 We could then obtain the location-specific minimum mortality
 1183 temperature (MMT), the reference for which the relative risks
 1184 at the 99th temperature percentile could be calculated. This
 1185 study considers the fraction of deaths related to non-optimal

1179 temperatures (Attributable fraction, or AF), which is defined
 1180 as follows:

$$1181 AF(t) = 1 - \frac{1}{RR(t2m(t))}, \quad [2]$$

1182 where the relative risk (RR) of the regional cumulative exposure-
 1183 response association, $RR(t2m)$, for a given temperature, $t2m$, at
 1184 a given time t , is calculated using the epidemiological association
 1185 defined above in Equation D. We specifically focus on HRM
 1186 defined as AF corresponding to temperatures above the MMT,
 1187 with the AF for temperatures below the MMT being set to 0. For
 1188 temperatures outside of the domain on which the epidemiological
 1189 association was fit we performed a log-linear extrapolation (41).
 1190 The AF forecasts were computed using the above described
 1191 epidemiological association applied to forecasts of temperature.
 1192 To compute the uncertainty associated with the epidemiological
 1193 fit we performed 1000 Monte-Carlo simulations (42) of the HRM
 1194 for each region, then separately aggregated the values in each
 1195 simulation to compute the median and 95% confidence interval.
 1196 The AF climatology was computed by calendar day using data
 1197 from 2010-2019 and smoothed with a 31-day running mean. The
 1198 seasonal-average AF was computed by averaging the daily values.
 1199 This is an approximation not accounting for the temporal variability
 1200 of the total number of deaths, and was provided as context for
 1201 a readership of diverse specialisations; for more comprehensive
 1202 studies we refer readers to (8, 9).

1203 **E. Forecast skill.** Forecast skill was assessed considering the lead-
 1204 time for which a forecast has a continuous rank probability skill
 1205 score (CRPSS) (43) exceeding 0.25. This "predictability horizon"
 1206 is akin to the lead-time up to which a forecast provides useful
 1207 information. We selected a threshold of 0.25 following ECMWF's
 1208 primary forecast evaluation metrics (for temperature at 850hPa)
 1209 (44) in order to facilitate comparison between results. Previously,
 1210 (17) used an alternate metric, which we discuss further in the
 1211 appendix. The CRPSS was calculated for each individual weather
 1212 forecast using all 51 members of the forecast ensemble (i.e. the
 1213 51 possible future evolutions of the weather over the coming
 1214 two weeks according to the forecast system). This means that
 1215 we calculate the CRPSS for every day in the summers of 2022
 1216 and 2023, and for every region and lead-time. It is a way of
 1217 comparing the performance of an ensemble forecast relative to
 1218 a baseline (here: climatology) which would represent the best
 1219 estimate of future weather in the absence of a forecast system.
 1220 A wholly accurate forecast has a CRPSS of 1; a value of 0
 1221 indicates that the forecast has no skill relative to a forecasting
 1222 system always predicting climatological values. Negative values
 1223 represent a misleading forecast, which performs worse than a
 1224 forecast predicting climatology. For details of the calculation
 1225 see the Appendix. To relate temperature and the temperature
 1226 predictability horizon to the AF predictability horizon, we use
 1227 a negative binomial regression. This was chosen to account for the
 1228 integer values of the predictability horizons, and so as not to assume
 1229 a priori a variance for each region. We use a seven-day running
 1230 mean to smooth the time series' of the predictability horizons. We
 1231 computed the 95th percent confidence intervals by resampling with
 1232 replacement 1000 times. All averages were computed with equal
 1233 weighting of values, unless otherwise stated.

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